

Building Interoperable Knowledge Graphs with X3ML Framework (a hands-on tutorial)

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Abstract

Knowledge graphs play a pivotal role in representing, integrating, and reasoning over complex heterogeneous data in a semantically rich and machine-interpretable way. They are increasingly used to enable interoperability across diverse domains. A critical step in the construction of knowledge graphs is the transformation of source data into RDF- aligned with domain ontologies- requiring robust and maintainable schema mapping approaches.

This tutorial presents X3ML Framework, a suite of specifications and tools designed to support the construction of knowledge graphs from structured data. At its core is a technology-agnostic, declarative schema mapping language that enables users to describe how elements of a source schema correspond to concepts and properties in a target ontology. The language is expressive, human readable and supports the collaborative generation of schema mappings. Moreover, the framework includes tools that facilitate schema mapping definition and a transformation engine that applies these mappings to source data, generating RDF aligned with the target ontology. Additionally, X3ML offers tools for exploring and verifying the generated knowledge graphs, helping users ensure the semantic correctness and completeness of their data integration workflow. The framework is domain-independent and has been widely adopted in projects across disciplines, including cultural heritage and biodiversity.

This tutorial will combine conceptual overviews with practical demonstrations, guiding participants through the complete workflow of defining schema mappings, and semantically integrating data to

construct knowledge graphs using X3ML. Attendees will gain hands-on experience with the tools, learn best practices and understand how to ensure semantic alignment with domain ontologies. The tutorial will also introduce innovative methods leveraging Large Language Models (LLMs) to accelerate the schema mapping process. These methods aim to reduce manual effort by assisting or automating the generation of mapping definitions. By the end of the session, participants will be equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to apply X3ML effectively in real-world scenarios, enabling them to build interoperable, semantically rich knowledge graphs.

Presenter

Yannis Marketakis is a R&D Software Engineer and Technical Manager at the Information Systems Laboratory and the Centre for Cultural Informatics of FORTH-ICS. He is also a PhD candidate and holds an MSc in Information Systems. His research interests include information systems, digital preservation, conceptual modelling and knowledge representation, semantic data integration, and software engineering for large-scale infrastructures. He has a vast experience in conducting applied research in the field of ICT. He has been actively involved in several European and national research projects contributing as lead R&D engineer. He is the co-author of more than 55 scientific publications and one book, and has presented his work at various international conferences. His contributions have been recognized with a Best Paper Award (MTSR'20). He brings deep expertise in the design and implementation of semantic data integration workflows for the construction of knowledge graphs.

Description

This tutorial focuses on the X3ML Framework, a widely adopted solution for defining schema mappings and realizing the transformation of heterogeneous data sources, towards constructing semantic knowledge graphs. The main objectives of the tutorial are to: (a) introduce X3ML framework

and its components, (b) instruct how to define schema mappings using X3ML mapping language, (c) demonstrate how to transform structured data into RDF knowledge graphs, (d) showcase strategies and best practices, and (e) equip attendees with practical skills for real-world application of X3ML Framework.

In addition to the core capabilities of the framework, we will also present emerging methods for accelerating the manual process of schema mapping process using Large Language Models (LLMs). These approaches can assist automating the generation of schema mappings, reducing the human intervention and improve productivity in collaborative semantic data integration workflows.

The outline of the tutorial is the following:

- **Introduction to Knowledge Graph Construction** (10 min)
- **Overview of the X3ML Framework** (40 min)
- **Use cases and Project Examples** (5 min)
- **LLM-based Schema Mapping Definition** (10 min)
- **Hands-on Session** (40 min)
 - Step-by-step definition of schema mappings
 - Data transformation process
 - Data exploration
- **Wrap-up and Discussion** (15 min)

The tutorial directly aligns with IJCKG 2025 topics, particularly (a) Knowledge Graph Construction and Integration, (b) Knowledge Graphs and Large Language Models, (c) Ontology Modeling and Evolution and (d) Knowledge Representation and Reasoning. It will be of high value to researchers, practitioners, and developers working on semantic technologies, and ontology-driven applications. By providing both conceptual insights and hands-on training, the session empowers attendees to apply a proven methodology for scalable and semantically robust data integration across various domains.

Target Audience

This tutorial is designed for:

- **Researchers and practitioners** involved in knowledge graph construction, semantic data integration and ontology engineering.
- **Data engineers, developers and students**, working with structured data (e.g. XML, relational databases) who wish to transform them into RDF using ontologies.
- **Domain experts and data curators**, participating in interdisciplinary projects that involve mapping diverse data collections.
- **Early-career professionals** in the areas of knowledge representation and semantic data integration.

It will be especially valuable for participants involved in projects related to cultural heritage and biodiversity domains, because of the wide adoption of X3ML in those domains.

No prior experience with X3ML is required.

Attendees are expected to have:

- General understanding of structured data formats and XPATH
- Basic familiarity with RDF and ontologies

Duration

The duration of the tutorial is 2 hours.

Previous Offerings

The tutorial has not been presented before.

Technical Requirements

No special equipment or software is required.

References & Links

- [1]. Marketakis, Y., Minadakis, N., Kondylakis, H., Konsolaki, K., Samaritakis, G., Theodoridou, M., Flouris, G. and Doerr, M., 2017. X3ML mapping framework for information integration in cultural heritage and beyond. *International Journal on Digital Libraries*, 18(4), pp.301-319.
- [2]. <https://github.com/isl/x3ml>